

Open Science Project 2024 - Harkonnen

Version 0

Description

DMP of the project for the Open Science course of the Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge Master's Degree.

The project aims at addressing the following research questions:

1. Is that possible to create a new index of citations which contains typed citations where a peer review (citing entity) reviews (specific citation function) a publication (cited entity)?
2. What is the necessary transformation of the [Crossref](#) dump necessary to create such an index to be compliant with the OpenCitations Data Model?
3. What are the top publication venues in terms of the number of peer reviews received?
4. How many peer reviews in Crossref are included in [OpenCitations Meta](#)?
How many articles that have been reviewed by a peer review are included in OpenCitations Meta?

Funder

University of Bologna

Grant

Open Science course 2023-24

Researchers

Matteo Guenci (orcid:0009-0006-3139-1667), Daniele Spedicati (orcid:0009-0002-8965-3480), Chiara Parravicini (orcid:0009-0006-7501-6789), Nicole Liggeri (orcid:0009-0006-9417-2648)

Organizations

University of Bologna, Italy

1. Main Info

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [University of Bologna](#)

Grants: [Open Science course 2023-24](#)

Project: [OpenScience 2024](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Description of the output dataset – PROCI Dump

Dataset resulting from the PROCI software workflow, processing of Crossref Peer Reviews according to OpenCitations Data Model.

Contains:

1. Citations.csv

file[oci]: OCI generated for the citation;

file[citing_doi]: DOI of the Peer Review involved in the citation;

file[cited_doi]: DOI of the Entity reviewed by the peer review;

file[citing_url]: url version of citing_doi;

file[cited_url]: url version of cited_doi;

file[citing_date]: date of creation of the citing entity;

file[timespan]: period between the creation of the cited entity and the citing entity.

2. Venue.csv

file[cited_doi]: DOI of the Entity reviewed by the peer review;

file[cited_venue]: Title of the venue in which the cited_doi is stored;

file[cited_issn]: ISSN (1..*) of the venue in which the cited_doi is stored.

3. Provenance.csv

file[oci]: OCI generated for the citation;

file[prov_agent]: agent responsible for the creation of the citation;
file[source]: URL of the source of the citation data;
file[prov_date]: date in which the citation instance is created.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

We are re-using data coming from [Crossref](#) and [OpenCitations](#).

In particular we are using the Public Data File from Crossref of [April 2023](#) (DOI:10.13003/8wx5k) and the [OpenCitations Index data dump - November 2023 Dump](#) (DOI:10.6084/m9.figshare.24416749.v2).

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Since our data is a result of a manipulation coming from already existing data it can be considered derived.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Three .csv files

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

200MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

OpenCitations Meta and Crossref

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-harkonnen-code>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Legal

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://schema.datacite.org/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024/tree/main/docs/Harkonnen>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

PROCI Dump

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The output will be accessible indefinitely through the dedicated repository which is shared with an ISC license

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The output will be accessible indefinitely through the dedicated repository which is shared with an ISC license

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

FAIR best practices

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

ISC License

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Nicole Liggeri (orcid:0009-0006-9417-2648)

Methodology - Drafting and implementing a comprehensive action plan to address project challenges.

Software - Contribution to the software dedicated to processing and postprocessing.

Validation - Verification of the general reproducibility of the project.

Writing - Review & Editing

Investigation - Research and gathering of previous Bibliography and Software.

b. Daniele Spedicati (orcid:0009-0002-8965-3480)

Methodology - Drafting and implementing a comprehensive action plan to address project.

Software - Implementation of Postprocessing and Data Analysis.

Validation - Verification of the general reproducibility of the project.

Formal Analysis - Statistical Analysis of final data.

Investigation - Research and gathering of previous Bibliography and Software.

Writing - Original Draft.

Vusualisation - Production of Charts.

c. Chiara Parravicini (orcid:0009-0006-7501-6789)

Methodology - Drafting and implementing a comprehensive action plan to address project challenges.

Software - Implementation of software dedicated to post-processing and data analysis; contribution to the processing phase.

Validation - Verification of the general reproducibility of the project.

Writing - Review & Editing.

d. Matteo Guenci (orcid:0009-0006-3139-1667)

Methodology - Drafting and implementing a comprehensive action plan to address project challenges.

Software - Implementation of software dedicated to processing data from Crossref.

Validation - Verification of the general reproducibility of the project.

Data Curation - Cleaning and preparing data for initial use.

Writing - Review & Editing

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

With a DOI assigned by Zenodo

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Description of the output dataset – PROCI Meta Comparison

Dataset from the PROCI software results with OpenCitations Meta dump (2024 April)

Contains:

1. meta_peers_cleaned.csv

file[DOI]: doi of citing entities in PROCI dataset also included in Meta.

2. meta_article_cleaned.csv

file[DOI]: doi of cited entities in PROCI dataset also included in Meta.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

We are re-using data coming from [Crossref](#) and [OpenCitations](#).

In particular we are using the Public Data File from Crossref of [April 2023](#) (DOI:10.13003/8wx5k) and the [OpenCitations Index data dump - November 2023 Dump](#) (DOI:10.6084/m9.figshare.24416749.v2).

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Since our data is a result of a manipulation coming from already existing data it can be considered derived.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Two .csv files

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1.5MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

OpenCitations Meta and Crossref

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-harkonnen-code>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Legal

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://schema.datacite.org/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024/tree/main/docs/Harkonnen>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

PROCI Meta comparison

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The output will be accessible indefinitely through the dedicated repository which is shared with an ISC license

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The output will be accessible indefinitely through the dedicated repository which is shared with an ISC license

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

FAIR best practices

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

ISC License

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Nicole Liggeri (orcid:0009-0006-9417-2648)

Methodology - Drafting and implementing a comprehensive action plan to address project challenges.

Software - Contribution to the software dedicated to processing and postprocessing.

Validation - Verification of the general reproducibility of the project.

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Software - Implementation of software dedicated to processing data from Crossref.

Validation - Verification of the general reproducibility of the project.

Data Curation - Cleaning and preparing data for initial use.

Writing - Review & Editing

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

With a DOI assigned by Zenodo

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Description of the output dataset – PROCI RDF

PROCI RDF statements.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: Dataset

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

We are re-using data coming from [Crossref](#) and [OpenCitations](#).

In particular we are using the Public Data File from Crossref of [April 2023](#) (DOI:10.13003/8wx5k) and the [OpenCitations Index data dump - November 2023 Dump](#) (DOI:10.6084/m9.figshare.24416749.v2).

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Since our data is a result of a manipulation coming from already existing data it can be considered derived.

1.1.5 What is its format?

.ttl

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

430MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

OpenCitations Meta and Crossref

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-harkonnen-code>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Legal

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://schema.datacite.org/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024/tree/main/docs/Harkonnen>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

PROCI Meta comparison

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The output will be accessible indefinitely through the dedicated repository which is shared with an ISC license

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The output will be accessible indefinitely through the dedicated repository which is shared with an ISC license

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

FAIR best practices

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

ISC License

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Nicole Liggeri (orcid:0009-0006-9417-2648)

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Vusualisation - Production of Charts.

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Software - Implementation of software dedicated to processing data from Crossref.

Validation - Verification of the general reproducibility of the project.

Data Curation - Cleaning and preparing data for initial use.

Writing - Review & Editing

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

With a DOI assigned by Zenodo

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Description of the PROCI software

The purpose of the software is to extract important data from the Crossref dump and then combine those data with data from Open Citation Meta. The aim is to create an output dataset that answers the following research question: "Is that possible to create a new index of citations which contains typed citations where a peer review (citing entity) reviews (specific citation function) a publication (cited entity)? What is the necessary transformation of the Crossref dump necessary to create such an index to be compliant with the OpenCitations Data Model? What are the top publication venues in terms of the number of peer reviews received? How many peer reviews in Crossref are included in OpenCitations Meta? How many articles that have been reviewed by a peer review are included in OpenCitations Meta?"

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Software

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

Several Python files that can be run from a single run.py file.

1.1.5 What is its format?

.py

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record

To share the results with OpenCitations in order to understand if there is the actual need to create an index of peer rev

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

It is a new original product

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

Yes

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Projects identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://schema.datacite.org/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-harkonnen-code>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Peer Review Open Citation Index (PROCI)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

It will be accessible through the above mentioned github repository which is shared through the ISC license.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The output will be available, after the project has ended, indefinitely.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

FAIR practices

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

ISC License

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Matteo Guenci (orcid:0009-0006-3139-1667)

Methodology - Drafting and implementing a comprehensive action plan to address project challenges.

Software - Implementation of the software dedicated to processing data.

Validation - Verification of the general reproducibility of the project.

Data Curation - Cleaning and preparing data for initial use.

Writing - Review & Editing

b. Chiara Parravicini (orcid:0009-0006-7501-6789)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Methodology - Drafting and implementing a comprehensive action plan to address project challenges.

Software - Implementation of software dedicated to post-processing and data analysis; contribution to the processing phase.

Validation - Verification of the general reproducibility of the project.

Writing - Review & Editing.

c. Daniele Spedicati (orcid:0009-0002-8965-3480)

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Methodology - Drafting and implementing a comprehensive action plan to address project.

Software - Implementation of Postprocessing and Data Analysis.

Validation - Verification of the general reproducibility of the project.

Formal Analysis - Statistical Analysis of final data.

Investigation - Research and gathering of previous Bibliography and Software.

Writing - Original Draft.

Vusualisation - Production of Charts.

d. Nicole Liggeri (orcid:0009-0006-9417-2648)

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Methodology - Drafting and implementing a comprehensive action plan to address project challenges.

Software - Contribution to the software dedicated to processing and postprocessing.

Validation - Verification of the general reproducibility of the project.

Writing - Review & Editing

Investigation - Research and gathering of previous Bibliography and Software.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Thanks to a DOI assignement performed by Zenodo

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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